

TEACHING STUDENTS SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING TO SUPPORT EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Goal 4 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals is to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”. Central to promoting lifelong learning is equipping students with Self-Directed Learning (SDL) skills such as metacognition and related motivational and volition skills (e.g. perseverance, grit). The Diploma in Chemical Engineering has used the Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate (CDIO) Engineering Education framework (www.cdio.org) and design thinking to redesign an integrated curriculum that supports both education for sustainable development (ESD) and SDL. In this curriculum framework, students learn via real world projects in which they Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate chemical product solutions using low-cost local materials and appropriate technology. In this process, they learn key subject content knowledge, thinking and learning skills as well as developing an experiential appreciation on how the knowledge and skills they acquire in their curriculum modules can be used to support sustainable development, other than to earn a career in the chemical processing industry. In this paper, we share a new initiative that aims to develop students’ SDL skills, and further support ESD via chemical product design. This involves progressive learning tasks that provide ongoing deliberate practice and feedback around these central curriculum aims. This initiative is facilitated in stages, over the entire course duration, using this integrated CDIO approach. In Year 1, we introduced a model of SDL that is explicitly taught to students. Central to this model is the systematic development of metacognition and a growth mindset. Strategies of direct instruction, modelling and stories (both from faculty and student experiences) reinforce the key learning strategies and skills and that successful learning is attainable with sustained effort. In Year 2, such skill development will be reinforced and extended through modules on chemical product design, leading to a Capstone Project in Year 3. This paper shares current work done in Year 1, presenting preliminary findings on our students’ learning experience using the SDL model; follow by plans for

Year 2. It concludes with an appraisal of what has been learned for enhancing pedagogic practice in this challenging curriculum area.

Keywords: *CDIO, self-directed learning, education for sustainable development, chemical product design*

Introduction

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals are a collection of 17 global goals as part of Resolution 70/1 of the UN General Assembly (UN, 2015). Of interest in the chemical engineering education is Goal 4: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”. In particular, Section 4.7 of Goal 4 read “By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture’s contribution to sustainable development”.

It is not possible for a 3-year diploma to address all these issues, so we put the emphasis for our curriculum on education for sustainable development (ESD). It aims to help people to develop the attitudes, skills, perspectives and knowledge to make informed decisions and act upon them for the benefit of themselves and others, now and in the future (UNESCO, 1997). ESD helps the citizens of the world to learn their way to a more sustainable future.

However, there is no universal model of ESD; and nuanced differences according to local contexts, priorities and approaches exist even when there was overall agreement on the concept (De Rebello, 2003). Sterling (2004) identified a range of educational responses to sustainability as shown in Table 1, and advocated the third approach, which he termed “sustainable education.” This constitutes an order of learning higher than that of ESD. He explained the concept as one that is not just a simple add-on of sustainability concepts to the curriculum, but a cultural shift in the way we see education and learning, based on a more ecological or relational view of the world. Rather than a piecemeal, “bolt-on” response which leaves the

mainstream otherwise untouched, it implies systemic change in thinking and practice, informed by what can be called more ecological thinking and values – essentially a new paradigm emerging around the poles of holism, systemic thinking, sustainability, and complexity.

Table 1. Three Levels of Education and Sustainability

Education about sustainability	First-order learning Emphasis is on content/knowledge-based learning within the dominant paradigm Assumes that meaning of sustainability can be clearly identified and taught as a separate subject Essentially ‘learning as maintenance’ of current paradigm
Education for sustainability	Second-order learning Emphasis is on ‘learning for change’ that includes content, but goes further to include values and capability bias Deeper learning: involves critical and reflective thinking about sustainability Assumed that we know clearly what values, knowledge and skills ‘are needed’ for change and while challenging the existing paradigm leaves it mainly intact
Education as sustainability (Sustainable Education)	Third-order, transformative learning Emphasis is on process and quality of learning, which is seen as an essentially creative, reflective and participative process Knowing is seen as approximate, relational and provisional, and learning is continual exploration through practice Shift is towards ‘learning as change’ which engages the whole person and learning institution Process of sustainable development or sustainable living is essentially one of learning, while context of learning is essentially that of sustainability

Sterling (2004) further contended that the role of higher education “...should not be predicated only on “the integration of sustainability” into higher education, because this invites a limited, adaptive, response ...we need to see the relationship the other way around – that is, the necessary transformation of higher education towards the integrative and more whole state implied by a systemic view of sustainability in education and society.” Vare & Scott (2007) further made the point that, “sustainable development, if it is going to happen, is going to be a learning process – it certainly won’t be about ‘rolling out’ a set of pre-determined behaviours”.

ESD in Existing DCHE Curriculum

Self-directed Learning and Sustainable Development

Barth, et al (2007) identified self-directed learning skills as one of the key competencies in sustainable development. Also Norden (2016).

Various authors had advocated the use of project-based learning to develop key competencies for sustainable development (e.g. Cörvers, et al, 2016; Brundiers & Wiek, 2013; Nation, 2008)

Cheah (2015, 2014) had earlier written about using chemical product design to engage students using the CDIO Framework to redesign the Diploma in Chemical Engineering, which resulted in the curriculum model that supports education for sustainable development as shown in Figure 1.

We further uses Design Thinking to enhance the “conceive” stage as shown in Figure 2. Cheah (2015, 2014) had further shows the correspondence between the ideals of sustainable development espoused in the Brundtland Report, which explained it as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN, 1987). Specifically, as shown in Figure 3, we draw parallels between the three circles of design thinking and three circles of sustainable development.

Figure 1. DCHE curriculum model for ESD using CDIO

Figure 2. CDIO Framework enhanced with Design Thinking

Figure 3. Relationship between elements of design and sustainable development

Revamped DCHE Curriculum for Self-Directed Learning

The DCHE curriculum undergone a major revamp in 2017 that results in a spiral curriculum (Bruner, 1960). The work done had been described elsewhere by Cheah & Yang (2018). For the purpose of this paper, we will focus on one aspect of the revamp, and that is the introduction of a model of Self-Directed Learning that is being explicitly taught to students. Knowles (1975) described self-directed learning broadly as “a process in which individuals take the initiative, with or without the help of others, to diagnose their learning needs, formulate learning goals, identify resources for learning, select and implement learning strategies, and evaluate learning outcomes’ (p. 18). The model, as shown in Figure 4, also incorporates key concepts of growth mindset (Dweck, 2006) and metacognition (Schraw, 1998).

Figure 4. DCHE Self-Directed Learning Model

Growth Mindset (Dweck, 2006) refers to the belief that intelligence can be developed. Students with a growth mindset understand they can get smarter through hard work, the use of effective strategies, and help from others when needed. It is contrasted with a fixed mindset:

the belief that intelligence is a fixed trait that is set in stone at birth. Metacognition (Schraw, 1998) refers to the awareness and understanding of one's own thought processes. Being meta-cognitive means to be aware of one's thinking, emotion/feeling & behaviour, and evaluating how well we are using the range of specific thinking skills, and taking necessary corrective action to plan, monitor, and assess one's learning process and performance.

ESD requires a sustained effort..... Boyer et al (2014) based on an extensive meta-analytic review of self-directed learning (SDL) research over 30 years, five countries, and across multiple academic disciplines; concluded that SDL is a useful tool to promote lifelong learning skills in students.

Figure 5. Progressive Learning via Spiral Curriculum

Various authors had written about the usefulness of project-based learning in teaching students SDL skills (e.g. Eggermont, et al, 2015; Johnson, et al, 2015). More importantly, our approach

Stewart (2007) had showed that SDL readiness was a key enabler for achieving learning outcomes from project-based learning, which are often open-ended, ambiguous and requires knowledge beyond what had been covered in the curriculum. Other outcomes may include desired graduate attributes such as ethical reasoning, cross-cultural awareness, etc.

The survey was administered to all 7 classes of Year 1 chemical engineering students who took the module, totalling 130. A total of 81 responses were received. However, some responses were not accepted as they are

deemed invalid. Notable are the following questions posed:

- A. Name one or more parts of the Self-Directed Learning Model you remember.
- B. Did the workshops for P5 and P6 helped you to appreciate the use of the Self-Directed Learning Model in gaining new knowledge? Why?
- C. Which one of the following best describes your learning experience with the Self-Directed Learning Model so far?

Questions A and B are open-ended. For Question C, students are required to select 1 of 8 responses from a drop-down list, comprising the following:

- It helps me to work out how to learn in a systematic manner
- It is useful when I need to learn something new/ complex
- I am not too sure yet as I do not have sufficient practice using it at this moment in time
- I think only some parts of it are useful to me
- It is too complex to make use of
- I do not see how it can be applied
- I have my own way of learning, which I think is good enough for me
- I do not see its relevance in helping me learn

The findings relevant to these questions are shown (where N = no. of valid responses):

In general, students are able to identify with the key steps in being a self-directed learner, and quite a number are able to mention metacognition as an important factor. However, despite the high positive responses, only about 73% of respondents found the 3 workshops useful (with 75 valid respondents). This may be due to the opinions of some students who are still ambivalent about the importance of SDL (with 80 respondents). Only about 56% of students reported understanding the potential benefits of SDL, while about 16% do not think so – 2.50% thought that it was too complicated, another 2.50% had no idea how to apply it, 6.25% felt that their own way of learning is superior, and 5.00% reported seeing no relevance of SDL in helping their learning.

**Self-Directed Learning and Sustainability Education:
Can Self-Directed Learning Save the Planet?**

Lorraine Lander

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As discussed earlier, there has been far more written on why we need sustainability education, than on how to do it and do it well. As Lange (2004) writes, sustainability education is not easy and few educators have training in how to do it. One challenge associated with sustainability education is its interdisciplinary nature, which is uncomfortable for both the educator and many students who are more used to discipline-based instruction in education settings.

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